

Historic Building Information Modelling (HBIM) from points clouds to the modelling of complex geometrical elements and thematic information

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Abstract

Heritage Building Information Modelling (HBIM) is a workflow that focuses on the creation of three-dimensional (3D) proprietary files from physical data such as point cloud laser scans or image surveys, as well as historical architectural data discovered in building archives and historical references. These files can be used for a variety of purposes. As a consequence of this, parametric objects that are packed with information and classes can be utilised in the process of asset management all the way through the conservation, repair, and maintenance (CRM) stages of a heritage building structure. However, information must first be gathered and stored in a single reservoir in order to manipulate and map each geometric building category with its corresponding building category. This will result in a full library of objects that can be used to analyse loads, redesign sections, repair, apply interventions, maintain, and operate the structure. Due to a lack of understanding regarding the subject of this study, "Chiesa di San Giacomo," and its primary function, it was challenging to acquire historical evidence for this thesis. This was one of the reasons why it was so difficult. Nevertheless,

we were successful in acquiring the information required for the investigation and in documenting the components of the roof of the study, which was our primary focus. The details of the model were crafted utilising the same building and woodworking techniques that were applied during the model's original creation. Utilizing BIM (Building Information Modelling) software like Revit was incredibly beneficial in the process of developing parametric families, which ultimately resulted in a simpler modelling process. This was in addition to the software's extensive material library, which provides the capability for any object to be allocated to the material that is most appropriate for it. The finished product will be a detailed 3D HBIM model of the roof of the church, replete with characteristics for the concealed items beyond the scanned surface, as well as dimensions, materials, and construction data. This model will be created using Revit. The completed model has the capability of generating cross-sections, details, and schedules, in addition to an analytical 3D model for structural study, which is necessary for ensuring the structure's safety and developing a maintenance plan for the preservation of the heritage building.

Dissertation:

Link for full text

Presentation video:

<https://youtu.be/8CdTrRtuqb8>

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